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Reuse of wood products: comparison of biogenic modelling approaches for LCA

L Van Gulck¹, D von Dufving^{1*}, L De Ligne², J Van den Bulcke² and M Steeman¹

¹ Department of Architecture and Urban Planning, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium

² Department of Environment, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium

*E-mail: david.vondufving@ugent.be

Abstract. Biogenic carbon refers to the CO₂ absorbed by trees during their growth, which remains stored in wood products when these are used in buildings. At the product's end of life, this carbon is immediately released if the wood is incinerated, whereas reuse extends its storage. Temporary carbon storage in wood products can play an important role in achieving climate goals. The environmental impact of wood products can be determined through life cycle assessment (LCA) but a key challenge is how biogenic carbon flows are accounted for. Existing biogenic carbon modelling approaches range from static and simplified to dynamic (accounting for time-dependent factors) and complex. The European Horizon project 'Woodstock' aims to develop a user-friendly LCA approach to model the biogenic carbon flows of products, integrating temporal aspects and which can evaluate construction solutions involving reused wood streams. A first step in this development is to gain insight into existing carbon modelling approaches. While literature has elaborately discussed and compared existing approaches, there has been little focus on how to treat biogenic carbon with the reuse of products. This paper evaluates how various biogenic carbon modelling approaches can distinguish between new and reused wood products and between their incineration and reuse. The static '0/0' and '-1/+1' approaches cannot make these distinctions. In contrast, the dynamic 'ILCD', 'GWP_{bio}' and 'DynLCA' approaches can, depending on their underlying assumptions. These assumptions include how the benefits of biogenic carbon uptake are allocated over multiple reuse cycles and whether new trees are planted only when applying new products or also when products are reused. This paper identifies key methodological issues in the context of wood reuse, proposes some initial solutions, and outlines areas for further research.

1. Introduction

As trees grow, they sequester CO₂ from the atmosphere through photosynthesis. This sequestered CO₂ is called biogenic carbon and remains stored in wood products when used in buildings. At the product's end of life (EOL), the biogenic carbon is released if the wood is incinerated or composted, whereas reuse can extend the period of carbon storage. The temporary carbon storage in wood applications can play an important role in achieving climate goals [1].

The environmental impact of a wood product can be determined through life cycle assessment (LCA). A key issue is how biogenic carbon flows are accounted for in LCAs.

Traditionally, LCAs take a static approach, assuming biogenic carbon neutrality for wood products: harvested wood is replaced by new trees, which sequester a comparable amount of CO₂ as will be released at the product's end of life. However, this static approach fails to consider aspects such as the benefit of delaying emissions and the time it takes for trees to regrow. To capture these time-dependent aspects, a dynamic LCA approach must be applied [2]. Existing dynamic approaches range from simplified and user-friendly to detailed and complex depending on how time-dependent aspects are taken into account.

The European Horizon project 'Woodstock' aims to promote climate-smart wooden construction practices in line with the New European Bauhaus initiative [3]. This includes encouraging the application of reused and underutilized wood streams. A key objective of 'Woodstock' is to develop a user-friendly LCA approach that considers important temporal aspects and that can evaluate the construction solutions proposed during the project. To achieve this, the first step is to review existing carbon modelling methods. While literature has already elaborately discussed and compared existing approaches [2,4,5], there has been very little focus on how to treat biogenic carbon with the reuse of products.

When applying a new wood product, sustainable forest management requires new trees to be planted to replace those harvested for use. However, this principle becomes less straightforward when reusing wood products. Therefore, the authors propose two scenarios: either no new trees are planted (since no trees need to be harvested), or new trees are planted, enabling forest growth and additional carbon sequestration. [6] argues that in LCAs a credit should only be given if the carbon removal is recent. However, does this mean reuse cycles should receive no credit for extending the period of carbon storage? This issue raises important questions about how much carbon uptake (or benefit) should be recognized when reusing products.

When reusing wood products, three potential life cycles (LCs) were selected by the authors, as shown in Figure 1. A new product can be reused at the EOL (LC1), a reused product can be reused again (LC2), or a reused product can be incinerated (LC3). If reused products are not credited for biogenic carbon uptake, this would mean LC1 has the benefit of uptake and the benefit of no release, LC2 has no uptake or release and LC3 has the disadvantage of no uptake and the disadvantage of release. This imbalance suggests that excluding credits for reused products may unfairly favour new products. It also raises the question whether it is necessary to consider the sum of multiple LCs rather than the impact of individual LCs when dealing with reuse.

Figure 1. Three possible life cycles (LC) in the context of reuse, referred to as 'reuse' LCs. The biogenic carbon flows are put in green.

This paper is a preliminary study to evaluate how various biogenic modelling approaches can make a distinction between new and reused wood products and between the incineration and reuse of wood products when focusing on biogenic carbon flows. The study identifies the strengths and weaknesses of each approach and highlights key methodological decisions. Additionally, it outlines critical aspects requiring a further in-depth analysis.

2. Methods

2.1. Research steps

This paper examines commonly discussed biogenic carbon modelling approaches in literature. Two static approaches are considered, referred to as the '0/0' and '-1/+1' approaches. One simplified dynamic approach, based on the ILCD Handbook, is included, along with two more detailed dynamic approaches, known as the 'GWP_{bio}' and 'DynLCA' approaches. In the next section, the LCA framework is set out in which the carbon modelling approaches are analysed. Afterwards the key principles of each approach are explained and compared. In section 3. *Results*, each approach is evaluated on how it can consider the reuse of wood products. Lastly, in section 4. *Discussion and conclusion*, important methodological aspects requiring further research are highlighted.

2.2. LCA framework

The LCA approach developed within the 'Woodstock' project will utilize the established LCA standard for construction products: EN 15804, as a basis for its methodological framework. Thus, the life cycle stages of a product are represented by modules (module A = production and construction, module B = use, and module C = end of life). Furthermore, the cut-off allocation approach is applied for reuse and recycling, meaning the loads and benefits of reuse and recycling are allocated to the next life cycle and secondary materials do not carry the impact from primary production. While EN 15804 adopts the '-1/+1' approach for biogenic carbon modelling, this paper explores alternative carbon modelling approaches. Lastly, it is important to note that this study only focuses on CO₂ emissions as part of attributional LCA's and considers the commonly used 100-year time horizon (emissions occurring beyond this period are not considered).

2.3. Overview carbon modelling approaches

The following paragraphs provide brief descriptions of the different biogenic carbon modelling approaches. For a more elaborate explanation, the authors refer to existing literature [2,4,5,7-11].

0/0 approach In the '0/0' approach, the wood product is assumed to be biogenic carbon neutral over its life cycle and there is no consideration of biogenic carbon uptake or release.

-1/+1 approach The '-1/+1' approach also considers biogenic carbon neutrality, but in contrast to the '0/0' approach, the biogenic carbon flows are tracked throughout the life cycle of the product. Biogenic carbon is taken up in module A (-1) and released in module C (+1), independent of the specific EOL treatment of the product.

ILCD The ILCD approach is an example of a ton-year approach [5], which calculates a credit (measured in kg CO₂ eq.) based on the number of years an emission is delayed. Various ton-year approaches exist [1], they share the same underlying logic but their specific method for the credit calculation differs.

The ILCD approach is outlined in [7]. This approach follows the '-1/+1' approach and a credit is given to delayed emissions by multiplying the emission by the number of years it is delayed (up to 100 years) and a weighting factor of -0.01. For example, if the wood product is incinerated in year 60, the credit is '-0.6' multiplied by the emission in 'kg CO₂ eq.'

GWP_{bio} The GWP_{bio} approach was developed by Cherubini et al. [8] and further extended by Guest et al. [9]. Within this approach, specific characterization factors (GWP_{bio}) for biogenic emissions are developed that consider how long the biogenic carbon is stored and the rotation period of the biomass (i.e., period of time needed for full biomass regeneration).

The biogenic CO₂ emissions from biomass combustion are multiplied by the GWP_{bio} factors to get their relative contribution to global warming in terms of 'kg CO₂ eq.' [8]. The longer the

storage period and the shorter the rotation period, the smaller the GWP_{bio} factor and thus the smaller the impact of biogenic emissions (the GWP_{bio} factor can also be negative, giving a credit).

While biogenic CO_2 emissions are multiplied by the GWP_{bio} characterization factors that consider the temporal aspects rotation and storage period, fossil CO_2 emissions are multiplied by traditional static GWP characterization factors. As a result, when all CO_2 emissions are combined into a single score (kg CO_2 eq.), static and dynamic results are mixed [10].

DynLCA In this approach developed by Levasseur et al. [11], the exact timing of the CO_2 emissions is considered by combining a dynamic inventory with a dynamic impact assessment. The dynamic inventory provides a yearly overview of the emissions due to the production and EOL treatment of the product and due to the forest flows. The dynamic impact assessment uses characterization factors that consider the specific year of the emissions: the later the emission occurs, the shorter the time horizon to assess its impact on global warming.

When considering the timing of the emissions, the moment of carbon sequestration in the forest must also be determined. There are two possible scenarios for this [2]. (1) The 'growth' scenario where it is assumed that the trees are fully grown before the use of the harvested wood product (carbon sequestration declared in module A). (2) The 'regrowth' scenario where it is assumed that an equal amount of the harvested trees would start to grow right after the production process (carbon sequestration declared in module B). The 'regrowth scenario' yields more conservative results and stimulates sustainable forest management (i.e., what is harvested must be regrown) [2]. Therefore, only this scenario is further considered in this study.

Table 1 provides a comparative summary of how various aspects are considered by the different biogenic carbon modelling approaches.

Table 1. Comparison biogenic carbon modelling approaches for LCA.

	STATIC		SIMPLIFIED DYNAMIC	DYNAMIC	
	0/0	-1/+1	ILCD	GWP_{bio}	DynLCA
Biogenic carbon neutrality	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Tracks carbon flows	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Considers storage period	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Considers rotation period	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Considers timing of emissions	No	No	No	No	Yes
Important benefit	Easy to use	Easy to use	Easy to use	Static inventory	Most realistic
Important drawback	Biogenic carbon not considered	Storage period does not matter	Overestimation benefits	Mix of static and dynamic results	Dynamic inventory: time- and data-intensive

3. Results

This section examines how each biogenic carbon modelling approach allows to differentiate between a new and reused wood product and between its incineration and reuse. Figure 1 illustrated the three possible 'reuse' LCs. These are compared against three corresponding 'new' LCs where a new product is used, followed by incineration at its EOL. The comparison between new and reuse LCs is conducted from two perspectives. First, the impact of each LC is assessed individually. LCAs typically focus on a single LC and this approach allows to determine the impact of each of the three possible reuse LCs. For these analyses, each LC is assumed to occur in the present, while the other LCs are treated as either past or future scenarios. For example, when evaluating LC3, LC2 and LC1 are assumed to have taken place in the past. Similarly, when assessing LC2, LC1 occurs in the past and LC3 in the future.

Second, the new and reuse LCs are compared by considering the cumulative impact of all three LCs. This approach avoids the need to allocate the benefits of biogenic carbon uptake across multiple LCs.

To support the analysis of each carbon modelling approach, figures are drawn up to illustrate the possible difference in carbon flows between the new and reuse LCs.

3.1. 0/0 approach

In this approach, biogenic carbon is not considered and therefore no differentiation can be made between new and reused products and between the different EOL treatments based on biogenic carbon. As illustrated in Figure 2, this limitation applies both when considering the impact of the individual LCs and the sum of the LCs.

Figure 2. Biogenic carbon flows (in green) with the new and reuse life cycles (LC) based on the '0/0' approach (N = new; R = reuse; Inc = incineration).

3.2. -1/+1 approach

In the '-1/+1' approach, the biogenic carbon stored in the product is released in module C (+1) regardless of the EOL treatment (i.e., incineration or reuse). Therefore, to ensure biogenic carbon neutrality over the product's life cycle, uptake must be considered in module A (-1) irrespective of whether the product is new or reused [12]. Figure 3 shows this approach does not distinguish between new and reused products, nor between incineration and reuse of a product. This holds true both when analysing the impact of the individual LCs and the cumulative impact of all LCs.

Figure 3. Biogenic carbon flows (in green) with the new and reuse life cycles (LC) based on the '-1/+1' approach (N = new; R = reuse; Inc = incineration).

In contrast to the '0/0' and '-1/+1' approaches, the biogenic carbon modelling approaches discussed in following paragraphs consider how long the carbon is stored in the product. Since reuse allows for a longer storage period, it is expected that these approaches can differentiate between new and reused products and between the incineration and reuse of products.

3.3. ILCD

According to the ILCD approach, a credit is given for the number of years a CO₂ emission is delayed. This means longer carbon storage periods should lead to higher credits. Figure 4 shows the possible credits for the new and reuse LCs. When assessing the impact of the individual reuse LCs, following question arises: the emission is delayed with 90 years in total leading to a credit of -0.9 kg CO₂ eq. per kg CO₂, how should this credit be distributed among the three reuse LCs?

If each reuse LC is credited solely based on its own duration, the result is identical to the credits for new LCs, failing to account for the prolonged storage enabled by reuse. Conversely, attributing each reuse LC the full storage credit of '-0.9' also does not seem fair. Especially for the first LC (LC1_R) since there is no guarantee on future actions. A more balanced approach might involve crediting each reuse LC based on its duration while also considering past and/or future LCs. Figure 4 outlines three potential options: Option a: each reuse LC credit is based on its duration and all past LCs. Option b: each reuse LC credit is based on its duration and one past LC. Option c: each reuse LC credit is based on its duration, one past LC and one future LC.

The choice of the 'best' option depends on various factors, such as the level of certainty about the other LCs. For instance, past LCs are often considered more certain than future ones. Notably, only option c differentiates between the reuse and incineration of a new product (LC1_R vs. LC1_N). However, all options involve double-counting benefits, which seems unavoidable if the goal is to distinguish between new and reuse LCs.

When considering the sum of all LCs, the credit calculation is more straightforward (i.e., -0.9 for the sum of both the new and reuse LCs). However, in this case, there is no differentiation between new and reused products and between incineration and reuse: the total credit for three short storage periods is the same as for one long storage period facilitated by reuse. To obtain a larger credit for the sum of the reuse LCs, the credits calculated for the individual reuse LCs could be summed. However, each option would result in a total credit exceeding -1 kg CO₂ eq. per kg CO₂ (i.e., more than 100%), which is not possible according to the ILCD approach.

Figure 4. Biogenic carbon flows (in green) with new and reuse life cycles (LC) based on the ILCD approach (N = new; R = reuse; Inc = incineration; Credit = number of years delay * 0.01).

3.4. GWP_{bio}

In this approach, biogenic CO₂ emissions from incineration are multiplied by the GWP_{bio} factor. Guest et al. [9] provide GWP_{bio} factors for different rotation and storage periods and a time horizon of 100 years. Figure 5 presents the possible GWP_{bio} factors for the new and reuse LCs, assuming an 80-year rotation period for the trees.

Figure 5. Biogenic carbon flows (in green) with new and reuse life cycles (LC) based on the GWP_{bio} approach (N = new; R = reuse; Inc = incineration; GWP_{bio} factors provided by [9]).

When analysing the impact of the individual reuse LCs, Figure 5 outlines several possible options.

Option a: since incineration only occurs in the last LC, the first two LCs (LC1_R and LC2_R) follow the '0/0' approach and only the last LC (LC3_R) is affected by the GWP_{bio} factor, based on the full 90-year storage period. As the storage period for LC3_R exceeds that of LC3_N, LC3_R has the lowest impact. Whether LC1_R and LC2_R have a lower impact than LC1_N and LC2_N depends on whether the GWP_{bio} factor is positive (resulting in an impact for biogenic emissions) or negative (resulting in a credit). In the example shown in Figure 5, the GWP_{bio} factors for the new LC are positive giving them a higher impact than the first two reuse LC. However, this approach raises the question if it is fair to only give the last reuse LC a credit for the long storage period enabled through the previous reuse LCs?

Options b to d in Figure 5 mirror the logic of the options presented with the ILCD approach. Option b: the storage period includes the duration of the LC and all past LC. Option c: the storage period covers the duration of the LC and one past LC. Option d: the storage period includes the duration of the LC and one past and one future LC. As with the ILCD approach, this could be considered double-counting of the storage benefits.

A more straight forward way to consider reuse within the GWP_{bio} approach is to consider the sum of the multiple LCs. Unlike the ILCD approach, the GWP_{bio} approach differentiates between multiple short storage periods and one prolonged storage period, making reuse more beneficial.

3.5. DynLCA

The DynLCA approach uses a dynamic inventory that tracks forest carbon flows. This requires determining whether new trees are planted only when a new product is introduced or also when a product is reused, as discussed in the introduction section. Both scenarios are explored in this analysis. Figure 6 illustrates the biogenic carbon flows that occur throughout the new and reuse LCs. All emissions occurring within the time horizon of 100 years are considered. Biogenic carbon uptake occurs during the LCs when a new tree is planted (represented by the rectangles) and biogenic release happens during incineration (represented by the arrows).

When considering the impact of the individual reuse LCs, two options are shown. In the first option, presented by green rectangles, a tree is planted only when a new product is introduced. If the tree has not reached its full rotation period by the time the product is reused, subsequent LCs can account for biogenic uptake during the remaining rotation period. Under this scenario, LC1_R has a lower impact than the corresponding new LC because it involves the same carbon uptake but no release. For LC2_R there is less uptake than the new LC but there is also no release. This may lead to a higher or lower impact depending on how long the rotation period of the first tree continues and the timing of emissions. Lastly, LC3_R, has a higher impact than the new LC since it only involves release without any uptake.

The second option when considering the individual LCs entails that new trees are also planted when the product is reused (green rectangle for LC1_R and blue rectangles for LC2_R and LC3_R). In this case, LC1_R and LC2_R have lower impacts than their corresponding new LCs because they involve the same carbon uptake but no release. LC3_R, however, has the same impact as the new LC since both involve equivalent uptake and release.

With the sum of the LCs, again the two options are considered for the reuse LCs. If no new trees are planted with reuse (only green rectangle), there is only one biogenic uptake and one biogenic release compared to three uptakes and three releases with the sum of the new LCs. A calculation example could help show how the exact timing of the emissions impacts the comparison between the sum of the new and reuse LCs. In contrast, if new trees are planted with reuse, the reuse LCs involve three biogenic uptakes and only one release. This clearly leads to a lower impact for the sum of the reuse LCs compared to the sum of the new LCs.

Figure 6. Biogenic carbon flows (in green and blue) with new and reuse life cycles (LC) based on the DynLCA approach (N = new; R = reuse; Inc = incineration). Green rectangles: new trees are only planted with new products. Blue rectangles: new trees are also planted when reusing products.

4. Discussion and conclusion

The '0/0' and '-1/+1' approaches assume biogenic carbon neutrality and do not differentiate between new and reused wood products or between their incineration and reuse. In contrast, other carbon modelling approaches can make these distinctions, depending on the underlying assumptions. For example, with the ILCD and GWP_{bio} approaches, determining the impact of the individual life cycles (LCs) requires deciding how much of the total storage time should be attributed to each LC. This could involve considering all past LCs, one past LC, or a combination of past and future LCs. Promoting reuse LCs required double-counting carbon benefits, revealing a methodological limitation needing future study. Within the scope of this study double-counting can be avoided by considering the sum of the LCs. However, in this case, the ILCD approach does not differentiate between consecutive short storage periods with new products and one long storage period enabled through reuse.

In the DynLCA approach, it is important to decide whether trees are only planted with new products or also when products are reused. If new trees are planted with reuse, the reuse LCs become clearly more advantageous than the new LCs. However, if trees are planted only with new products, the relationship between the reuse and new LCs depends on the length of the LCs, rotation period of the trees and exact timing of the emissions. Planting new trees after every rotation period could also be considered, independent of using new or reused products.

Both when analysing individual LCs and when summing them, assumptions must be made about past and/or future LCs. However, LCA practitioners traditionally perform LCAs for a single LC with little insight into previous LCs and no guarantees on future ones. Furthermore, this paper focused on how carbon modelling approaches could be used to promote reuse. However, under the cut-off allocation approach, reused products already benefit from not carrying a production impact, and reusable products are not assigned a disposal impact. This raises the question whether an additional benefit through biogenic carbon is necessary for the reuse of products.

The goal of this paper was not to identify the best carbon modelling approach in the context of reuse but rather to analyse the possibilities and limitations of existing approaches. It aimed to highlight key methodological issues and propose some initial solutions. The options explored for the ILCD, GWP_{bio}, and DynLCA approaches are non-exhaustive and represent the most apparent possibilities. Other methods to allocate biogenic carbon uptake over the reuse LCs exist and require further research. Future studies will include a more in-depth discussion on this topic and will involve calculation examples to quantify the implications of methodological decisions.

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